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TOPOLOGICAL IMAGE OF A PHASE DIAGRAM $CsVO_3 - Cs_2WO_4 - Cs_2O$ AND ITS TRIANGULATION

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The purpose of this article is to study the ternary system and its triangulation. The preliminary theoretical analysis of the ternary system $CsVO_3 - Cs_2WO_4 - Cs_2O$ made it possible to reduce experimental studies to a minimum. There are many difficulties in identifying equilibrium solid phases in complex systems, so it is necessary to have knowledge of phase levels and their regularities in multicomponent systems. Rational methods for the study of multicomponent systems are presented by is a theoretical analysis of the composition diagram and subsequent experimental studies of its main elements, the choice of which depends on the goals of the experiment.

The triple system has been experimentally studied and triangulated. As a result, nine triangulation cross-sections were identified, which divide them into 10 subsystems, which are quasi-three-component and triple systems.

Solid-phase synthesis of individual compounds was carried out [1-6], their compositions were studied, 4 main subsystems were identified, which were combined as new materials, as a result of which cesium bronzes were obtained. Cesium bronzes are used as anti-corrosion coatings, high-activity ion-electronic conductors, and deciphering catalysts.

Keywords: triangulation, diagram, compounds, crystallization, synthesis, phase, cross-sections, forecast, complexation.

Experimental part.

For the study, differential thermal analysis (DTA) [9] and visual polythermal analysis (VPA) [10] using the projection-thermographic method (PTHM) [11-12] in platinum crucibles was used, Pt-Pt/Rg thermocouples served as a temperature meter.

To record DTA curves, a device based on the F-116 electronic automatic potentiometer with voltage amplification was used. The calibration of the unit was carried out according to the temperatures of phase transitions of individual salts and their eutectic mixtures, recommended in [9]. On the STA 409 PC (Luxx) synchronous thermal analyzer from Netsch, derivotographic analysis was performed, designed to simultaneously measure the temperature, as well as to record changes in the weight of the weights in a wide range of temperatures (25-1500 °C). Monitoring of the measurement process was carried out by a built-in device connected to a personal computer. X-ray phase analysis (XRF) of the initial data [13] and the resulting compounds was carried out using the Dron-20 diffractometer [14]. XRF samples were fired at 630°C for 60 h followed by quenching. The measurement limits were $.2 \times 10^{-2}$ with a constant time of $2.1 = 15$ m and 30 kV. Identification of phase compositions was carried out

according to Hiller's tables and the ASTM card index [15].

We used pre-dehydrated reagents of qualification "HC", "chda". All compositions are expressed in molecular percentages, the temperature is in °C. The indifferent substance was freshly calcined of the "c.d.a" grade. The weight of the attachments was 0.1-0.3 g. Al_2O_3

Results and discussion.

This system is part of the ternary oxide system, which $CsVO_3 - Cs_2WO_4 - Cs_2OCs_2O - V_2O_5 - M_0O_3$ we identified as a result of its preliminary triangulation. The topological image of its phase diagram, constructed on the basis of its faceting elements, is characterized by the presence of three congruently and four incongruently melting binary compounds on the faces, which are divided into four subsystems (I-IV) and conditionally (V-VIII) subsystems. Fig. 1(D_1, D_2, D_3)

A priori prognosis of its phase complex made it possible to assume that there is a realization in NVT, 4 of which are eutectics and 4 peritectics To delineate the surface of liquidus by the WPA method, 17 internal sections were studied Table 1 (13), Fig. 2 (26). In order

to clarify the characteristics of the HT (Table 2) $(E_1 - E_4)(P_1 - P_4)$. [14], the upper liquiduses of the system were plotted on the side (Fig. 3). For all formulations, the heating and cooling were removed by the DTA method, In addition, bar-radiographs were taken on the Dron-20 diffractometer (Cu, K, L - radiation = 0.154 nm, Ni filter). $Cs_2O - CsVO_3$

Based on the results of experimental studies, the forecast on the number and nature of HTT was confirmed. [7,8] This made it possible to construct an experimental model of the phase diagram and delineate the fields of crystallizing phases.

The surface of the liquidus is represented by crystallization fields of 10 phases (Fig. 3

Rice. 1. Topological image of the phase diagram of the system $CsVO_3 - Cs_2MoO_4 - Cs_2O$

The analysis obtained from the phase diagram allows us to conclude that the phenomenon of NVT transfer to the neighboring subsystem is observed in the system (a change in the nature of the phase formation process, which is difficult to predict in systems with developed complexation. In particular, the PIE2 curve (Fig. 2) is eutectic up to the point d of intersection with the triangular section D3- Cs_2MoO_4 , i.e. the E2d segment, and the processes on the dP are peritectic. In the same way, the following curves are used: P3P2E3

(p3P2p- peritectic processes; a and E3 - eutectic); The diagram also shows that the initial components and binary complexes of the molybdate are well mutually soluble in a wide range of temperatures and concentrations.

These complexes are binary (vanadate D3), molybdates (s3, S4) and triple vanadatomolybdates (D, S, S2) complex oxide phases, each of which retains its volume of crystallization in the concentration triangle (Fig. 2).

Table 1

Internal sections of the CsV03- Cs2Mo04- Cs20 system

№ Section	Composition of the initial substances, mol. %	Additional component Mol. %	t pl °C	Crystallizing Phase
I	5 Cs20-95 CsV03	12 Cs2Mo04	357	S1+ CsV03
		17 Cs2Mo04	322	D1+ S1
		49 Cs2Mo04	376	Di1+ S4
		86 Cs2Mo04	390	S2+ Cs2Mo04
And	20 Cs2O-80 CsV03	12.5 Cs2Mo04	350	S1+ D2
		20 Cs2Mo04	330	s3+ s3
		28 Cs2Mo04	309	S3+D1
		49 Cs2Mo04	356	D1+ S4
		80 Cs2Mo04	370	S2+ Cs2Mo04
III	34 Cs20-66 CsV03	14 Cs2Mo04	444	D2+ s3
		30 Cs2Mo04	327	S3+D1
		50 Cs2Mo04	335	s2+ s4
		72 Cs2Mo04	363	S2+ Cs2Mo04
IV	45 Cs20-55 CsV03	15 Cs2Mo04	420	D3+ s3
		30 Cs2Mo04	345	s4+ s4
		52 Cs2Mo04	326	s2+ s4
		65 Cs2Mo04	355	S2+ Cs2Mo04
V	52 Cs20-48 CsV03	16 Cs2Mo04	389	D3+ S3
		29.5 Cs2Mo04	355	S4+ s4
		54 Cs2Mo04	333	s2+ s4
		62 Cs2Mo04	348	S2+ Cs2Mo04
VI	65 Cs20-35 CsV03	19 Cs2Mo04	303	D3+ S3
		30 Cs2Mo04	376	s3+ s4
		60 Cs2Mo04	341	s4+ S2+ Cs2Mo04(Pi)
VII	75 Cs20-25 CsV03	16 Cs2Mo04	319	Cs20+ D3
		24 Cs2Mo04	301	Cs20+ S3
		33 Cs2Mo04	390	S3+ s4
		70 Cs2Mo04	357	S4+ Cs2Mo04
VIII	87,5 Cs20-12,5 CsV03	30 Cs2Mo04	357	S3+ Cs20
		39 Cs2Mo04	408	S3+ S4
		78 Cs2Mo04	397	S4+ Cs? Mo04
IX	90 Cs2O-10 Cs2Mo04	16 CsV03	390	Cs20+ D3
		57 CsV03	606	D3+ D2
		85 CsV03	500	D2+ CsVO3
X	80 Cs2O-20 Cs2Mo04	21 CsV03	319	Cs20+ D3
		55 CsV03	521	D3+ D2
		78 CsV03	341	D2+ CsV03
XI	50 Cs2O-50 Cs2Mo04	42 CsV03	332	S3+D1+S4(P2)
		63 CsV03	330	S3+S!
		74 CsV03 .	346	Si+CsV03
		74 CsV03 .	346	Si+CsV03
XII	34 Cs20-66 Cs2Mo04	35 CsV03	327	S4+ D1
		57 CsV03	309	D1+ S3
		66 CsV03	302	S1+ S3
		73.5 CsV03	342	S1+CsV03
XIII	15 Cs20-85 Cs2Mo04	1.5 CsV03	420	S4+ Cs2Mo04
		20 CsV03	360	S2+ Cs2Mo04
		41 CsV03	356	s2+D,
		68 CsV03 .	318	D.+ S,
		74 CsV03	351	S)+CsV03
XIV	35CsV03-65 Cs2Mo04	21 Cs20	, 326	s2+ s4
		49 Cs20	390	s3+ s4
		69 Cs20	322	S3+ Cs20
XV	45 CsV03-55 Cs2Mo04	10 Cs20	356	D]+ S2
		22 Cs20	327	Di+ S4
		46 Cs20	376	s4+ s3
XVI	60CsVO3 -40 Cs2Mo04	57 Cs20	301	S3+ Cs20
		33 Cs20	327	Di+ S3
		53 Cs20	303	S3+ D3
		70 Cs20	368	D3+ Cs20
XVII	90 CsVO3-10 Cs2Mo04	16 Cs20	333	CsV03+ D2
		37 Cs20	580	D2+ D3
		83 Cs20	425	D3+ Cs20

Table 2.

Characteristics of the NVT system CsV03- Cs2Mo04- Cs20

HBT	T pl °C	Composition, mol.%			Crystallizing phases
		CsV03	Cs2Mo04	Cs20	
E ₁	288	25	20	55	Cs20+ D1+S3
E ₂	320	30	50	20	S2+S4+ D1
E ₃	300	66	24	10	S3+ D1+ S1
E ₄	330	75	Yu	15	CsV03+ Si+ D2
p ₁	341	14	60	26	S4+ Cs2Mo04+ S2
p ₂	332	42	30	28	Di+ S4+ S3
RZ	443	59	14	27	Si+ D2+ S3
P ₄	457	52,5	14,5	33	D2+ S3+ D3

Fig 2. System Composition Diagram CsV03- Cs2Mo04- Cs20

Rice. 3.

Projection of the liquidus surface of the $CsVO_3$ - Cs_2MoO_4 - Cs_2O system on the double side of Cs_2O - $CsVO_3$

Findings

Using the methods of prediction and modeling of topology and analysis of phase formation in faceted elements, triangulation of a triple system of triangulating cross-sections, which are divided into subsystems that are quasi-binary and triple oxide-salt systems, was carried out. Based on the aggregate of the results of thermal, X-ray phase and topological analysis, a geometric model of the system composition diagram was constructed. $Cs_2O - V_2O_5 - MoO_3$

Based on the results of experimental data, molybdenum bronzes of cesium were obtained. These compositions are promising in the processing of new materials, in particular anti-corrosion coatings; high-activity ion-electronic conductors; nanoselective catalysts; electrodes for potentiometric redox and acid-base titrations, electro-optical materials.

References:

- Zhigalov V.S. Solid-Phase Synthesis of Thin-Film Materials Siberian State Aerospace University named after M. F. Reshetnev, - Krasnoyarsk: Siberian State Aerospace University named after M. F. Reshetnev, 2011. 124 p. (in Russian).
- Israpilov M-A.M. Topology and Phase Formation in the Cs_2O - V_2O_5 - MoO_3 Ternary Oxide System: Abstract of Diss. - Makhachkala, 2009. - 23 p.
- Babaev E.V., Ermoatyev D.S. Ros. Mendeleev Chemical Journal 2009, vol. 53, no. 5, p. 42
- O'Donneet Zhon C. Scott W.L.J. Am Chem Soc 1996V. 118 P. 6070-6071
- Denisova E.N. Solid-Phase Synthesis of Metal-Melting Powders Ekaterinburg: USTU-UPI, 2008. - 64 p. (in Russian).
- Ridgway Z.M. Harrison L. Educational System and computers, 2011 vol. 3, pp 995-1000, Dol 1007/978-3-642-21747-0 129
- Gasaliev A.M., Akhmedova P.A., Differentiation of multicomponent systems - Makhachkala: DGPU, 2011. - 145 p.
- Kraeva, A.G., Davidova, D.S., Pervikova, V.N., Methods of Splitting Diagrams of the Composition of Multicomponent Mutual Systems with Complex Connections Using Computer Graphs, Report of the USSR Academy of Sciences, 1972, vol. 202, no. 4, pp. 850-853.
- Berg A. Introduction to thermography. Moscow, Nauka Publ., 1969, 195 p.
- Bergman A.G. Polythermic Method for the Study of Complex Salt Systems. All-Union Mendeleev Congress on Theoretical and Applied Chemistry. - Kharkov-Kiev: GNTI, 1935. Vol.2, Issue 1.-P.631-637.
- Kosmynin A.S. Projection-Thermographic Method of Studying Heterogeneous Equilibria in Condensed Multicomponent Systems. In-t general and non-organic. Department of Chemistry named after N.S. Kurnakov. - Moscow: [b. i.], 1977. - 15 p.,
- Wendlandt, W.U. Thermal Methods of Analysis - Moscow: Mir, 1978. - 526 p. :
- Trunov V.N., Kovba L.M. X-ray Phase Analysis - Moscow: Moscow Publishing House. University, 1976. - 232 p. (in Russian).
- Giller, Y.L. Tables of interplane distances, Moscow: Nedra, 1966. - 2 volumes; 362 p. (In Russian).
- Index Powder Diffraction Files. ASTM. N.-Y. Pennsylvania, 1975.